

SOCIAL SCIENCIES

MILTON'S SONNETS VII AND XIX: AN EXPLICATION

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Abstract

In this study, I will examine what comes over John Milton's creative productivity using the early-written Sonnet VII and the late Sonnet XIX. Sonnet VII is about time and how it rushes by, whereas Sonnet XIX is about Milton's blindness. We can see the severity and depth of literary matter from the content of each sonnet; however at the end of each sonnet, Milton becomes more aware of his problem, his God, and even the remedy.

Although there are many nice lines in Milton's early poems, especially those written before 1632, they are not particularly noteworthy. As a result, when he writes Sonnet VII, he finds that he has accomplished very little of what he had anticipated. In this short article, I'll analyze and contrast these two sonnets: VII and XIX, and discuss how they reflect key characteristics and poetic contrasts in Milton's early and late poetry.

Keywords: Milton, sonnet, VII, time, XIX, blindness

Introduction

John Milton (1608-1674) is a famous literary figure. He is known for his masterpieces *Paradise Lost* and *Paradise Regained*. In addition, he has written twenty three sonnets; two of them are Sonnet VII and Sonnet XIX. Griffith (1991) claims that these two sonnets are among the best written sonnets (p. 39). Lawry (1968) has referred to "the Sonnet 19 and the early Sonnet 7" as good examples to compare between "the early and the late poems" written by Milton (pp. 16-17). In this short article, a comparison between these two sonnets will be applied. The goal is to understand Milton and the change that has taken place in his poetry. This study of Milton's two sonnets uses the method of close reading where the focus will be on details in order to understand the meaning of the text in question. Burke (2020) defines close reading as "thoughtful, critical analysis of a text that focuses on significant details or patterns in order to develop a deep, precise understanding of the text's form, craft, meanings, etc." (p. 2). Hence, these two sonnets will be explained and analyzed line by line to achieve this goal.

Discussion

"How Soon Hath Time," a Sonnet by John Milton, portrays vivacity, freshness, light, and other qualities associated with a young man. On the other hand, Sonnet XIX, "When I Consider...", addresses major issues such as blindness, doubt, sorrow, and struggle. These are topics for a wise and experienced man. Anyhow, in order to understand these two sonnets in light of what has been mentioned above, it is preferable to examine and explain each sonnet separately, then compare and contrast the differences, changes, and similarities that occur in these two sonnets.

A. Sonnet VII:

On December 9, 1631, Sonnet VII was most likely written. John Milton's twenty-third birthday is on this day. His "three and twentieth year!" is mentioned in the sonnet. Pattison, 1889, argues that it is written on Mil-

ton's birthday. It's written for a buddy who has chastised Milton for his insatiable desire to study. He has traditionally preferred reading and learning. As Macaulay (1935) points out, it's possible that his studies were the cause of his blindness later on (p. 115). Anyhow, this sonnet is considered an autobiographical poem as the poet utilizes the first person: "my", "I", and "me". However, "it is also clearly intended to instruct its readers and to help them manage their anxieties" (Roy, 2021).

Although the last three lines rhyme d c e instead of c d e, hence it's a Petrarchan sonnet. This rhyme reveals Milton's concern for time, despite the fact that he appears patient and knowledgeable of fate and God's purpose of his creation. The lines of this sonnet are written in iambic pentameter. In this sonnet one-syllable words prevail. This gives the sonnet a more musical tone in general. Most nouns, such as time, youth, year, manhood, and so on, have their own connotations. Along the sonnet, there are terms like "three and twenty year," "late," "so near," "less," "ripeness," and so on that keep time in mind.

The personification of "time" at the start of Sonnet VII, by the way, retains its depiction in mind throughout the poem. Milton sees "time" as a thief of youth with wings. He has stolen Milton's "three and twentieth year" on his wings. Here, "he personifies time with a bird, which takes his age away on its wings" (beamingnotes.com contributor). "But my late spring neither bud or blossom show'th," Milton says of that year's "spring." The term "spring" can refer to a season (which is significant to the year) or a fountain of pleasant water. Plants will benefit from the presence of a fountain. Here's a question: when Milton says "fountain," what exactly does he mean, and how does that fit into the context? He could be referring to something (poetry) that irrigates people's thoughts. As Honigmann (1966) argues that Milton uses "bud or blossom" to refer to poetry (p. 98). Otherwise, he's referring to the time when a little of work has been accomplished.

Indeed, Milton expresses regret that he lacks a profession or "career" in line three. When he says "bud or blossom," he means that he thinks his career should be poetry and how to water other people's thoughts. His output is low, despite the fact that he is getting older. One's age can sometimes be deduced from his appearance. The term "may" in line five alludes to the rarity of such a scenario, however it proves to be true for Milton, who matures early. As a result, he claims, "my resemblance might deceive the truth."

Moreover, Milton demonstrates how he has grown into his manhood. Manhood is affirmed by the ripeness of the mind. Despite this, he complains that his "inward ripeness" has resulted in fewer works than those of others his age who have completed more. Those "more timely-happy spirits," according to Honigmann (1966), are among his contemporaries, such as Randolph (b. 1605), Abraham Cowley (b. 1618), and others who published works by that age (p. 96). Thus, in the octave, Milton appears to be lamenting the passage of time, which has robbed him of his age, despite the fact that others cannot notice. He also bemoans the fact that he has produced fewer works than others at his age.

However, Milton becomes patient throughout the sestet, employing one-syllable expressions to express his faith in fate, whether it be chance or God's plan. Line 12 implies that time, in its natural course, will bring about the outcome that is predetermined. Under the Creator's guidance, both chance and God's will may be employed, and Milton aspires to be able to use both to serve his God. It is his destiny; he will "wait and see the grace of the 'Task-Master,' or God, anticipate for his blessings that may his fortunes change into better someday" (beamingnotes.com contributor). The term "Task-Maker" at the end of the sonnet indicates that Milton believes that everything is pre-arranged and pre-planned by God.

In general, Milton begins talking about time and how it passes in Sonnet VII. Then, he becomes conscious of fate in the sestet, and he is patient and wishes to serve God. This occurs in the octave as a result of his "manhood" and "inward ripeness."

B. Sonnet XIX:

Milton's Sonnet XIX, on the other hand, is about his hindrance, which is blindness. In 1652, he became completely blind, which could be the year this sonnet was written. He'd learned a lot by this point. His blindness is most likely due to his learning and education. While Sonnet VII was written to defend his learning and studies, Sonnet XIX is written to lament his blindness; he is asking God for help and makes it obvious that losing his sight has made it difficult for him to do anything.

In fact, Sonnet XIX is a Petrarchan sonnet in terms of structure and form. Its rhyme scheme ABBA ABBA CDE CDE is completely Petrarchan, implying Milton's understanding and knowledge of his circumstances. The lines are written in iambic pentameter. Because most words consist of one syllable, it has a big impact on the reader. Milton's skill to use words to convey his message may be seen in this style of writing.

In this sonnet, Milton also employs "monetary exchange" terminology, as Lawrence (1992) points out:

"spent," "exact," "account," "one," and "thousands" (pp. 271-73). He also utilizes words that imply time, such as "when," "days," "spent," "soon," "present," and so on. These connotative words convey a variety of meanings and concepts to readers. In addition, words like "death," "light," "ocean," and others are employed.

Anyhow, Milton laments his eyesight at the start of Sonnet XIX, claiming that he does not anticipate losing his sight until "half" his "days." His "sight is spent" at the age of forty-three or a year older. The word "spent" connotes both giving and taking; he is implying that the one who has given him the eyesight, i.e. God, is now taking back that sight. Everything is dark after he loses his sight. Milton refers to his world as "this dark world" in the second line of the sonnet. The word "consider" at the start, on the other hand, suggests that he is pondering. According to Raupp (2020), "when Milton loses his physical sight, he gains spiritual light, which he expresses in the sonnet" (p. 26). As a result, the reader will not be surprised by Milton's conclusion.

The servant who has not obeyed his lord in benefiting from his "talent" in Matthew XXV is afterwards remembered by Milton. According to Nicolson (1963), the metaphor for the sonnet is "the unprofitable servant" was thrown out into darkness for burying the money his master had given him in the dirt (p. 153). The term "talent" is a pun in Sonnet XIX. It does not refer to money; rather, it refers to the "inward ripeness" stated in Sonnet VII. Indeed, both the servant's money and the "inward ripeness" are gifts from God, according to Milton. Milton's gift is his "inward ripeness," which he describes as "death to hide." It is hazardous to keep knowledge hidden from others; knowledge should be shared. He is defending his case and complaining to God at the same time. He believes he is ineffective because he lacks authority (sight). His soul, on the other hand, argues that he must serve his Creator. His soul compels him to serve his "Maker and present [his] true account," as he puts it. According to Sasek (1981), "his blindness [has] caused him to develop a new image of himself" (p. 17).

Furthermore, Milton asks the following question to clarify his point and stress his dilemma: "Doth God exact day-labor, light denied?" This question adds to the poem by stating his thesis and counter-argument: "Doth God exact day-labor," is the case, and "light denied" is the counter-argument. "I fondly ask," Milton quickly apologizes after explaining the case and defense. The reader might expect line 8 to continue the question, but the conjunction "but" follows that and shifts the focus. This enjambment, especially the one that connects lines 8 and 9, creates some kind of discord: "...But patience to prevent / That murmur..." An idea is expected to be in the sestet, however the phrase "but" mingles both octave and sestet. In the octave, Milton laments the injustice of his predicament, and patience appears to respond to his query. According to Brilsby (2018), "Patience is not a virtue of truth; it is a virtue of endurance. Patience only aims 'to prevent / That murmur', not to prove the murmur is groundless."

Patience is personified in the following lines. She arrives to stop the nonsense and states, "God doth not used / Either man's work or his own gifts" (Lines 9-10).

God does not employ man's work or his own skills. "His State / Is Kingly": the sestet affirms that Milton needs God's help, but God doesn't need anyone: "His State / Is Kingly." Everything is carried out at His command. Thousands of angels serve Him under His command, "And post o'er Land and Ocean without rest" (Line 13). Finally, Milton makes his confession of faith: he wishes to serve God, if only by accepting his orders and waiting for them to be fulfilled. Angels and those who "stand and wait" are both serving God in this way.

C. Comparison

Returning to the first point made at the outset of this article, Milton's two sonnets, VII and XIX, share certain parallels and have distinctions as well. Milton is a man of vast knowledge, as evidenced by his writing. In these two sonnets, his ideas are expressed explicitly through melodic music that provides harmony and concord to the sonnets.

Each sonnet examines and explores a problem. Sonnet VII deals with time whereas blindness has been addressed in Sonnet XIX. In the first sonnet, Milton recognizes that time will carry out what has been predetermined, so he waits until "Time leads [him]..." at the end of this poem. In Sonnet XIX, his patience pays off and answers his inquiry. Finally, he realizes that God does not require anyone's help. As a result, he chooses to serve God. Due to the point that Milton's focus is on serving God in some way, that idea raises the question, "What does it mean to serve God?" (Piper, 2020).

Milton, on the other hand, is concerned about his output, writing "no bud or blossom" in Sonnet VII and "Lodg'd with me useless" in Sonnet XIX. Well, "when he could see, he wasted his sight. Now that he is blind, he fears—he knows—his remaining powers are 'Lodg'd in [him] useless'" (Brilsby, 2018). However, Sonnet XIX casts a dark shade; Milton bemoans his blindness and laments to God. Asad (2015) argues that Milton has had "faith in God for assisting him in his quest for greatness" in 'How Soon Hath Time' while "he lovingly accepts god's will in his divine scheme of things" in 'On His Blindness.' As a result, this sonnet depicts a powerful battle of pain and struggle. Sonnet VII, on the other hand, implies a youthful poem with a bright shadow (Lawry, 1968, p. 16).

Both sonnets rely on the reader's willingness to respond (Lawry, 1968, p. 17). Milton wishes to produce in Sonnet VII, but time has robbed him of his age. Here, "he personifies time with a bird, which takes his age away on its wings. Finally, he realizes that time is full of fate and destiny. In Sonnet XIX, there is a debate regarding whether or not to serve in the middle of the sonnet. God, on the other hand, does not need anybody and/or his/her service. As a result, Milton realizes that he must accept His directives and wait for them to be fulfilled.

Conclusion

Finally, both sonnets VII and XIX exhibit some of Milton's evolving poetic styles. Youth, brightness, activity, to some extent simplicity, and optimism are all presented in Sonnet VII. Strong struggle, originality,

sincerity, and to some extent pessimism characterize Sonnet XIX. And this shift is to be expected depending on the subject matter I examined in these two sonnets. Yet, there is a sense of religious bent; Milton has faith in his Task-Maker to guide him at the end of Sonnet VII whereas he ends up with embracing his limits and accepting God's will in Sonnet XIX.

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